

Remediation of arsenic polluted soil using ornamental plants *Caladium bicolor*

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ABSTRACT

Agricultural intensification causes excessive use of fertilizers and pesticides. Even though fertilizer and pesticides are suspected contain arsenic heavy metal. One of the efforts to reduce arsenic contamination from the soil by using ornamental plants is Caladium bicolor. The aim of this research is to determine the ability of Caladium bicolor to accumulate arsenic metal. The research using pots with a completely randomized design (CRD) consisted of four treatments of arsenic concentration with three replications. In this experiment using arsenic-contaminated soil from previous research activities with 4 levels of contamination, namely Control (without contamination), low contamination (5 ppm), moderate contamination (10 ppm), and high contamination (20 ppm). The collection of soil samples and plant samples for metal arsenic analysis was carried out before planting and after 9 weeks of age. The result showed that Caladium bicolor can reduce arsenic levels in the soil with the highest decrease of 19.43% in high level. Caladium bicolor able to accumulate arsenic in plant tissue that is the root and leaves. Judging from the growth of Caladium bicolor plants, the control treatment has a better growth than other treatments.

Keywords: *Caladium bicolor*, arsenic

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural intensification causes excessive use of fertilizers and pesticides. Even though fertilizers and pesticides are suspected contain arsenic heavy metal. According to Setyorini et al., (2003) several types of fertilizers containing arsenic such as N fertilizer, P fertilizer, manure, lime, and compost with contents of 2.2-120, 2-1200, 3-25, 0.1-25 and 2-52 mg/kg. Several types and active ingredients of insecticide and fungicide such as Dursban 200 EC, Antracol 70 WP, Bamex, 50SC Reagents, Curacron, Prevathon 50 SC, Agrimec 18 EC, Decis 2.5 EC, Dithane M-4/Detazeb 80 W indicated contain arsenic in the pesticide (Fikri et al., 2012).

One effort to reduce heavy metal contamination from the soil by using plants called phytoremediation. Phytoremediation is the use of plants to move, reduce or degrade hazardous substances which are environmentally friendly,

cost-effective and adaptive remediation technologies (Marmioli, 2001). Phytoremediation can use ornamental plants. In addition to aesthetic value, ornamental plants are not consumed so it is safe. All plants have the ability to absorb metals but in varying amounts. Some types of ornamental plants such as *hanjuanglandong* (*Cordyline frucosa*), *sambang dara* (*Excoecaria cochinensis*), *lidah mertua* (*Sansevieria trifasciata Prain*) were able to absorb Pb metal from the ground (Haryanti et al., 2013). *Lidah mertua* also could reduce the Cd content from the soil up to 44.01% (Yusuf et al., 2015). Ulimma et al (2016) reported that *hanjuang plants* (*Cordyline frucosa*), *heliconia* (*Heliconia psittacorum*) and *lidah mertua* (*Sansevieria trifasciata Prain*) could absorb mercury metal. *Caladium sp* plants could accumulate mercury metal up to 20 mg/kg (Muddarisna et al., 2015). *Reynoutria sachalinensis* and *Chlamydomonas sp.* has the potential to remediate arsenic-contaminated land and waters with an accumulation capacity of more than 2 g As/kg dry weight (Feller, 2000 in Hidayati, 2005).

Research on the remediation of arsenic using ornamental plants, especially ornamental taro (*Caladium bicolor*) has not been widely done. Therefore, more in-depth research is needed to determine the ability of *Caladium bicolor* to accumulate arsenic metal.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in 2017 in the greenhouse of the Indonesia Agricultural Environmental Research Institute. The study using pots with a completely randomized design (CRD) consisted of four treatments of arsenic concentration with three replications.

In this study using arsenic-contaminated soil from previous research activities with 4 levels of contamination namely control (without contamination), low contamination (5 ppm), moderate contamination (10 ppm), and high contamination (20 ppm). Planting of *Caladium bicolor* has done for 9 weeks. The collection of soil samples and plant samples for the analysis of metal arsenic was carried out before planting and after the plants were 9 weeks old.

Furthermore, soil and plant samples were prepared and analyzed for their metal content. Metal analysis using wet ashing method by adding a strong acid HNO₃ and HClO₄-. Measurement of arsenic metal using the Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) with a hydrid system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The soil used for experiments was from soil of previous research. The results of the analysis of metal arsenic on the initial soil before planting was presented in table 1. After planting 9 weeks of *Caladium bicolor*, there was a decrease in arsenic levels in the soil. The highest decrease in high arsenic

treatment was 19.43%, whereas in the control soil it contained arsenic from the soil-forming host rock. The earth's crust layer contained arsenic around 1.8 mg/kg (Kabata-Pendias, 2011). Levels of arsenic in the treatment of moderate and high could be reduced further by increasing the planting season of *Caladium bicolor*.

Table 1. Percent of Descending Arsenic in Soil

Treatment	Early Arsenicmg kg ⁻¹	Finall Arsenic	Percent of Descending Arsenic (%)
Control	1.37	1.22	11.03
Low	1.97	1.64	16.51
Moderate	2.49	2.18	12.63
High	3.93	3.17	19.43

The ability of plant to accumulate metal from the soil could be calculated with the value of Translocation Factor (TF) and Bio-concentration Factor (BCF). TF value <1 showed a greater metal translocation to the root than the canopy (Table 1). The amount of absorption of metals in the roots greater than canopy because the roots are plant organs that are direct contact with the soil. BCF values between 0.1-1 indicated that *Caladium bicolor* plants was medium accumulator in absorbing arsenic metal. Heavy metals in the soil could be bound by plants when in the form of ions in soil solutions or in the form of complex organic compounds that dissolve (Saeni et al., 1997 in Adji, 2005). Metals absorption mechanism from soil by plants as follows (Chaney et al, 1995 in Hidayati, 2005): (1) rhizofiltration, the ability of roots to absorb contaminants from the soil/groundwater, (2) phytostabilization, immobilization of contaminants in the soil by root exudates (3) phytostimulation, the ability of plants to stimulate biodegradation activity by microbes associated with roots, (4) phytoextraction and phytotransformation, the ability of plants to absorb contaminants then translocated to various organs of plants, (5) phytomining, the ability of plants to absorb metals with large amounts from soil. Plant physiological response to metals is by forming a protein that forms a binding compound called phytochelatin (Haryati et al., 2012 in Haryanti et al., 2013). Phytochelatin is a peptide containing 2-8 amino acids cysteine at the center of the molecule and a glutamic acid and a glycine at the opposite end. Phytochelatin is formed in the nucleus which then passes through the endoplasmic reticulum, the Golgi apparatus, and the secretory vascular to reach the cell surface.

Table 2. Arsenic concentration in root and leaves of *caladium bicolor*, TF and BCF of *caladium bicolor*

Treatment	Root mg kg ⁻¹	Leaf mg kg ⁻¹	Translocation Factor	Bioconcentration Factor
Control	0.34	0.17	0.50	0.25
Low	0.79	0.18	0.23	0.40
Moderate	1.17	0.20	0.17	0.47
High	1.20	0.21	0.18	0.31

The effect of heavy metals on plants can be seen from the physical plant characteristics such as plant height, leaf area and plant weight. Judging from the growth of plants, control treatment had the largest leaf area compared to high contaminant treatment (table 3). Although the number of leaves with low treatment had the highest number of leaves but the leaf area was still lower compared to control plants. Dry weight of plants with low treatment had greater than control because plants with low treatment had more leaves. Plants when absorbing heavy metals will form an enzyme in the root membrane. Enzyme activity will be inhibited due to the presence of metal ions. Arsenic inhibits the phosphorylase enzyme group (Edwards et al, 1980 in Hidayati, 2005). Enzyme activity will be inhibited due to the presence of metal ions. The response to metals occurs in inhibiting root and canopy growth and decreasing the rate of transpiration (Gerth, 2000 on Hidayati, 2005).

Table 3. Growth of *Caladium bicolor*

Treatment	Sum of Leaves	Wide of Leaves (cm ²)
Control	7	79.3
Low	11	73.0
Moderate	8	66.3
High	8	49.9

CONCLUSIONS

Caladium bicolor was able to accumulate arsenic in plant tissue on the root and leaves. *Caladium bicolor* could reduce arsenic levels in the soil with the highest decrease of 19.43 % in high level. Judging from the growth of *Caladium bicolor*, the control treatment had a better growth rate than other treatments.

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REFERENCES

- Adji, S. S. 2005. Rehabilitasi tanah sawah tercemar logam berat Pb dan Cd melalui fitoremediasi. *Jurnal Matematika, Sains dan Teknologi.*, **6**(2).
- Fikri E., O. Setiani, and Nurjazuli. 2012. Hubungan paparan pestisida dengan kandungan Arsen (As) dalam urin dan kejadian anemia (Studi : Pada petani Penyemprot Pestisida di Kabupaten Brebes). *Jurnal Kesehatan Lingkungan Indonesia.*, **11**(1):29-37.
- Haryanti D., D. Budianta, and Salni. 2013. Potensi beberapa jenis tanaman hias sebagai fitoremediasi logam Timbal (Pb) dalam tanah. *Jurnal Penelitian Sains.*,**16**(2).
- Hidayati, N. 2005. Fitoremediasi dan potensi tumbuhan hiperakumulator. *Jurnal Hayati.*, **12**(1).
- Kabata-Pendias, A. 2011. *Trace Elements in Soils and Plants Fourth Edition.* CRC Press.
- Muddarisna and Krisnayanti. 2015. Selection of Mercury Accumulator Plants for Gold Mine Tailing Contaminated Soils. *Journal of Degraded and Mining Lands Management.*, **2**(3).
- Marmioli N. 2001. Phyto 2000 : From The Enthusiasm For A Scientific Research To The Public Acceptance of An Innovative Technology. Intercost Workshop On Bioremediation.
- Ulimma R., I. Apriani and S. Siahaan. 2016. Skripsi : *Potensi Tanaman Hias Dalam Meremediasi Tanah Tercemar Merkuri (Hg).* Universitas Tanjungpura. Pontianak.
- Setyorini D., Soeparto and Sulaeman. 2003. *Kadar Logam Berat Dalam Pupuk. Prosiding Seminar Nasional Peningkatan Kualitas Lingkungan dan Produk Pertanian: Pertanian Produktif Ramah Lingkungan Mendukung Ketahanan dan Keamanan Pangan.* Pusat Penelitian dan Pengembangan Tanah dan Agroklimat. Badan Penelitian dan Pengembangan Pertanian. Jakarta.
- Yusuf M., A. Zubair, and A. Arsyad. 2015. Skripsi : *Fitoremediasi Tanah Tercemar Logam Berat Pb dan Cd Dengan Menggunakan Tanaman Lidah Mertua.* Universitas Hasanudin, Makasar.